

FUNDAMENTALS OF DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL THINKING AND EXTREME COMPETENCIES OF VOCATIONAL EDUCATION STUDENTS

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Abstract: *In the context of the rapidly changing modern labor market, the training of highly qualified, proactive specialists capable of making independent decisions in complex situations is becoming an urgent task facing the vocational education system. Today, the rapid renewal of production technologies, increased competition, and an increase in dangerous and uncertain situations require the development of not only theoretical knowledge, but also well-formed professional thinking and extreme competencies in students of vocational education.*

Key words: *Professional, competence, security, thinking, skill, competence, knowledge, extreme, individual.*

In the context of the rapidly changing modern labor market, the training of highly qualified, proactive specialists capable of making independent decisions in complex situations is becoming an urgent task facing the vocational education system. Today, the rapid renewal of production technologies, increased competition, and an increase in dangerous and uncertain situations require the development of not only theoretical knowledge, but also well-formed professional thinking and extreme competencies in students of vocational education.

Professional thinking is the student's ability to analyze professional problems, approach them creatively, and draw conclusions. This quality serves as the basis for a specialist to achieve success in professional activity, adapt to innovations, and be able to think independently. Extreme competencies include the skills of making the right decisions in emergency situations, ensuring safety, managing stress, and controlling the situation. These competencies are especially important for future specialists working in high-risk sectors such as industry, transport, energy, and construction.

Today, the terms "competence" and "competency" have already entered the education system of various countries. The concept of competence within the framework of security is not only knowledge in the field of security, but also the ability to apply it in practice, to be responsible and professional. People with this quality play an important role in building a safe society.

Thus, the meaning of the concepts "competence" and "competency" refers to the practical application of a set of knowledge, personal learning, traits, qualities, a measure of readiness for practical activity, the ability to solve problems, achieve the necessary results in practice, the integrity of knowledge, skills, and abilities that ensure professional activity in the individual, a set of activated learning, knowledge, and experience applied in practice, purposefully directed emotional and volitional strength of the individual, and other qualities [1].

Based on the analysis of materials on the history of the emergence of competence in education, the history of its development can be conditionally divided into four periods. First period (1960 - 1970s). During this period, the words "competence" and "competency" began to enter scientific literature for the first time. From this period, research related to the content of competence began, and D. Hans introduced the concept of "communicative competence" [2].

Second period (1970-1990). During this period, the categories of competence (competence) began to be used in the theory and practice of scientific research, professional skills in management, leadership, management, and the study of communication; The concept of "social competence (competence)" began to enter science [3]. This period is characterized by the fact that in various manifestations of competence, the categories "be ready," "ability" are presented, as well as such psychological qualities as "responsibility," "confidence" are noted. J. Raven in his work "Competence in Modern Society," published in 1984, gives a broad definition of competence. This is such a phenomenon that "it consists of a large number of components, many of which are independent of each other, some components belong more to the cognitive sphere, others to the emotional sphere. These components can complement each other in effective self-regulation".

Based on the foregoing, learning to perform refers not only to acquiring professional skills, but also to achieving a level of competence in a broad sense and the ability to successfully navigate complex situations arising during the process [4]. Such basic competencies also include effective teamwork, planning, problem-solving, creativity, leadership, entrepreneurship, organization, and communication skills.

Moreover, competence is connected with basic qualifications, not just with the basis of skills. At the same time, it is important to competently determine the basis of skills. These are personal and interpersonal qualities, knowledge, skills and abilities, manifested in many situations and in various forms in social life, work.

The third period began in the 90s of the 20th century, during which many research works were carried out on the application of competence as a scientific category in relation to education.

The fourth stage is associated with the inclusion of a competency-based approach in the content of standards of professional education and general professional disciplines. State Educational Standards (SES) define competence as follows: "Competence represents a set of knowledge, skills, abilities, and personal qualities that allow communication participants to perform various actions aimed at specific reasons and goals they set."

Most of these research works are based on the implementation of the concept of "cognition," in which it is established that students master a certain set of knowledge, skills, and abilities that serve to develop the level of cognitive activity.

A competency-based approach is understood as the formation of skills to create conditions for mastering a set of competencies in the education system [5]. This means that graduates' potential, abilities, and broad opportunities for stable activity in modern multifaceted socio-political, market, and economic conditions are created. "Competence" refers to the description of people with high knowledge and experience [6].

A person competent in a certain field possesses relevant knowledge, skills, and abilities, which allows them to act effectively in this area. Nevertheless, to date, the concept of "competence" in the world educational community does not have a sufficiently clear content to describe the desired image (professionally qualified model) of a graduate of a particular level of education.

In recent years, the concept of "competence" has also entered the sphere of professional disciplines. Orientation towards the results of the priority direction of education based on extreme competence is defined as the formation of the necessary general and professional competencies, self-determination, sociability, personal development, and self-expression. This approach is aimed at ensuring the quality of education in accordance with the needs of modern society, which corresponds not only to the need of individuals to participate in social activity, but also to the need of society itself to use the capabilities of the individual.

In the literature, the concept of "competence" is often manifested as a description of functional areas of activity and behavior. Thus, competence is a method consisting of knowledge, skills, abilities, and fundamental abilities that allow achieving success in a certain type of activity. According to P. Borisov, competence is the main characteristic of a person, which manifests itself in ensuring the effective or excellent performance of a given task.

Competence means a person's internal motivation for the high-quality implementation of professional activity, as well as the presence of professional values and an attitude towards their profession as a value. In this understanding, competence includes three aspects: knowledge, methods of activity and readiness to carry out

activity, self-development. By developing professionally, such a specialist creates something new, even in a small amount, bears independent responsibility for the decision made, and can set goals based on their value foundations.

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